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**МЕХАНІЗМИ РОЗВИТКУ ТА КОРЕКЦІЇ НІТРОЗАТИВНОГО СТРЕСУ У
ТКАНИНАХ ПАРОДОНТА ЩУРІВ ЗА УМОВ ОЖИРІННЯ ТА ХРОНІЧНОГО
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Summary. ¹Tsebenko M. O., ¹Bilets M. V., ¹Omelchenko O. Ye., ²Spivak M. Ya., ¹Neporada K. S. **MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT AND CORRECTION OF NITROSATIVE STRESS IN PERIODONTAL TISSUES OF RATS UNDER OBESITY AND CHRONIC STRESS CONDITIONS.** - ¹*Poltava State Medical University*, ²*D.K. Zabolotny Institute of Microbiology and Virology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*; e-mail: tsebenkomari@gmail.com. The purpose of the work is to determine the content of biomarkers (namely, nitric oxide, peroxynitrite and S-nitrosothiols) of oxidative-nitrosative stress which is of crucial importance in the pathogenesis of pathological changes in periodontal tissues in conditions of obesity and chronic stress, and also to substantiate the use of nanocerium. The combined effects of obesity and chronic stress lead to a maximum increase in the overall activity of NO synthases in the periodontal tissues of rats, particularly the inducible form (iNOS), which increases by 2.42 times compared to controls. Under these conditions, the concentration of peroxynitrites increases by three times, and the level of S-nitrosothiols increases by 1.2 times compared to these parameters in control rats. In the periodontal tissues of animals with chronic stress and obesity, the activity of ornithine decarboxylase increases by 1.6 times, and arginase activity rises 3.5 times compared to the control. Administration of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide to animals with combined obesity and stress significantly reduces iNOS activity by 2 times, overall NO synthase activity by 1.7 times, and the concentration of peroxynitrites by 3.5 times compared to rats with combined obesity and stress

without correction. Nanocrystalline cerium dioxide prevents the development of nitrosative stress, prevents alveolar ridge resorption, as confirmed by the reduction of the molar root exposure coefficient in all experimental groups. The results obtained suggest the potential use of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide for the prevention and treatment of pathological changes in periodontal tissues induced by combined obesity and chronic stress.

Key words: nanocerium, obesity, chronic stress, periodontium, alveolar ridge, nitric oxide, peroxynitrite, S-nitrosothiols, oxidative stress, arginase, ornithine decarboxylase.

Реферат. Цебенко М. О., Білець М. В., Омельченко О. Є., Співак М. Я., Непорада К. С. **МЕХАНІЗМИ РОЗВИТКУ ТА КОРЕКЦІЇ НІТРОЗАТИВНОГО СТРЕСУ У ТКАНИНАХ ПАРОДОНТА ЩУРІВ ЗА УМОВ ОЖИРІННЯ ТА ХРОНІЧНОГО СТРЕСУ.** Мета роботи – визначити вміст біомаркерів (а саме, оксиду азоту, пероксинітриду та S-нітрозотіолів) окислювально-нітрозативного стресу, який має вирішальне значення у патогенезі патологічних змін тканин пародонту в умовах ожиріння та хронічного стресу, а також обґрунтувати застосування наноцерію. Поєднана дія ожиріння і хронічного стресу призводить до максимального підвищення загальної активності NO-синтаз у тканинах пародонта щурів, зокрема індукцйбельної форми (iNOS), яка зростає в 2,42 рази порівняно з контролем. За цих умов концентрація пероксинітридів збільшується у 3 рази, а рівень S-нітрозотіолів – в 1,2 рази порівняно з цими показниками у контрольних щурів. У тканинах пародонта тварин з хронічним стресом на тлі ожиріння підвищується активність орнітиндекарбоксилази у 1,6 рази та аргінази у 3,5 рази порівняно з контролем. Введення нанокристалічного діоксиду церію тваринам із поєднаною дією ожиріння і стресу сприяє зниженню активності iNOS у 2 рази, загальної активності NO-синтаз у 1,7 рази та концентрації пероксинітридів у 3,5 рази порівняно з щурами, яким моделювали поєднану дію ожиріння і стресу без корекції. Нанокристалічний діоксид церію попереджає розвиток нітрозативного стресу, запобігає резорбції альвеолярного відростка щелеп, що підтверджується зниженням коефіцієнта оголення коренів молярів у всіх досліджуваних групах. Отримані результати свідчать про перспективність використання нанокристалічного діоксиду церію для профілактики та лікування патологічних змін у тканинах пародонта, спричинених поєднаною дією ожиріння та хронічного стресу.

Ключові слова: наноцерій, ожиріння, хронічний стрес, пародонт, періодонт, альвеолярний відросток, оксид азоту, пероксинітрид, S-нітрозотіоли, оксидативний стрес, аргіназа, орнітиндекарбоксилаза.

Introduction. Obesity is a global issue, recognized as a pandemic by the World Health Organization back in 1997. Currently, nearly 2 billion people worldwide are overweight. According to the STEPS study, 59.1% of Ukraine's population is overweight, one of the highest rates among Eastern European and Central Asian countries. The average weight of Ukrainian women was 73.6 kg, and men—82.1 kg. The mean Body Mass Index (BMI) of adults was 26.8 kg/m², increasing with age from 24.2 kg/m² in the 18–29 age group to 29.0 kg/m² in the 60–69 age group [1]. Data from the State Statistics Service of Ukraine indicate that the average weight of Ukrainians has increased by 2 kg, primarily among individuals over 50 years old. In 2008, the average weight of adult Ukrainians was 73 kg, rising to 75 kg in 2021. The imbalance between energy intake and expenditure, along with age-related, hormonal, genetic, environmental, and social factors, contributes to the obesity epidemic in Ukraine [2]. Moreover, over the past three years, the population of Ukraine has been under significant psycho-emotional stress due to the full-scale war. Thus, these two medical and social issues—obesity and chronic stress—are particularly relevant for us.

Previously [3], we demonstrated that excessive consumption of monosodium glutamate leads to hypothalamic neuron excitotoxicity, disrupting the lipostat mechanism, increasing appetite, and ultimately resulting in weight gain. This, in turn, contributes to obesity and its complications, including pathological changes in periodontal tissues. Similar studies [4] confirm that hyperinsulinemia and metabolic disturbances caused by obesity can significantly increase the risk of chronic inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues.

Nitrosative stress is one of the key mechanisms of tissue damage in many pathological

conditions. Reactive nitrogen species (RNS), such as peroxyxynitrite, play a critical role in chronic inflammation. By inducing nitrosative stress, they modify and degrade biopolymers in tissues, thereby exacerbating disease progression. Chronic stress is an important factor that intensifies nitrosative modifications and biopolymer catabolism. Prolonged exposure to stressors activates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and elevates cortisol levels, which, in turn, induces oxidative stress. According to [5], chronic stress stimulates inflammatory responses and disrupts metabolic homeostasis, leading to changes in periodontal tissues. Under conditions of metabolic syndrome and stress, the levels of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species significantly increase, promoting oxidative-nitrosative stress.

Recent studies have shown that nanocrystalline cerium dioxide possesses potent antioxidant properties, capable of reducing oxidative and nitrosative stress levels in the body. These nanoparticles act as catalysts, neutralizing excessive reactive oxygen and nitrogen species and preventing cellular damage [6] demonstrated that cerium dioxide can suppress oxidative processes and reduce inflammation, making it a promising agent for the treatment of inflammatory diseases such as periodontitis. Other studies confirm that nanocrystalline cerium dioxide improves tissue regeneration and protects cells from damage caused by stress and metabolic disturbances.

Intriguing findings from [7, 8] revealed that cerium dioxide nanoparticles exhibit neuroprotective properties, preventing neuronal damage during oxidative stress. This may provide protective effects not only in periodontal tissues but also in the central nervous system. Such multifunctional activity of cerium dioxide makes it a promising agent for the prevention and treatment of diseases associated with nitrosative stress.

Regarding periodontal diseases, current research confirms the connection between oxidative stress and periodontitis progression. [9] indicate that systemic conditions such as obesity and stress can exacerbate periodontal inflammation and tissue destruction. Similar conclusions were drawn by [10, 11], who noted that nitrosative stress activity is significantly elevated in patients with periodontitis, particularly those with metabolic disorders.

Thus, considering the current understanding of the mechanisms of nitrosative stress, obesity, and stress syndrome, as well as the potential of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide for their correction, the relevance of this study is undeniable. It will deepen our understanding of the pathogenesis of periodontal tissue diseases under obesity and stress conditions and aid in the development of new approaches for their prevention and treatment using nanocerium.

The purpose of the work is to determine the content of biomarkers (namely, nitric oxide, peroxyxynitrite and S-nitrosothiols) of oxidative-nitrosative stress which is of crucial importance in the pathogenesis of pathological changes in periodontal tissues in conditions of obesity and chronic stress, and also to substantiate the use of nanocerium.

Materials and methods

The experiments were conducted on 77 non-linear white rats of both sexes in compliance with the bioethical principles of the "European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes" [12], Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Council (2010), and the Law of Ukraine "On the Protection of Animals from Cruelty" (No. 3447-IV of February 21, 2006, Article 26), as well as the "General Ethical Principles of Animal Experimentation" (Kyiv, 2001–2019), as certified by the Bioethics Committee of PSMU (protocol No. 181 of 26.03.2020, No. 225 of 21.03.2024). The experiments modeled glutamate-induced obesity, chronic stress, individually and in combination. Obesity modeling was achieved through postnatal subcutaneous administration of monosodium glutamate to newborn rats [13] at a dose of 4 mg/g on days 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 after birth. The rats in the control group were subcutaneously injected with physiological saline at a dose of 8 µl/g. Throughout the experiment, the animals were kept in the PSMU vivarium under zoohygienic rules and maintained on a 12/12-hour day-night cycle with continuous aeration, an ambient temperature of 26°C, and humidity at (43±2)%. The rats received a mixed grain-vegetable diet and water ad libitum.

Body weight, BMI, and Lee Index were monitored weekly throughout the experiment. Chronic stress was modeled according to Hans Selye's method by immobilizing the animals on their backs for 5 hours during the final week before sacrificing the animals, which was performed 24 hrs after stress under thiopental anesthesia through exsanguination.

Starting from the first month after birth and continuing for three subsequent months,

experimental rats were administered nanocrystalline cerium dioxide (2–7 nm, stabilized with sodium citrate) orally via a gavage tube at a dose of 1 mg/kg dissolved in injection-grade water, with a volume of 2.9 ml/kg according to the following regimen: daily administration for two weeks followed by a two-week break.

For biochemical studies, the soft periodontal tissues were homogenized in 10 mM Tris-HCl buffer with pH 7.4, and the supernatant was used for biochemical assays. All manipulations were conducted at 0° to +4°C (on an ice bath). The following were determined in the periodontal tissue homogenates: Arginase and ornithine decarboxylase activities, total NO synthase activity and isoforms [14], Nitrite levels [15], Nitrosothiol content [16], Peroxynitrite concentration [17].

The degree of alveolar bone resorption was assessed using a binocular microscope with an eyepiece micrometer to calculate the molar root exposure coefficient, expressed as $\Delta L/L \times 100$, where L is the distance from the marginal edge of the alveolar ridge to the upper edge of the tooth crown, and ΔL is the distance from the marginal edge of the alveolar ridge to the lower edge of the crown (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Measurements were performed for each of the three molars using a stereomicroscope with an eyepiece micrometer

Statistical analysis of unpaired biochemical research parameters was conducted using non-parametric ANOVA with Bonferroni correction. All statistical calculations were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 26. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and their discussion

Biochemical studies of the soft periodontal tissues of rats subjected to glutamate-induced obesity, chronic immobilization stress, and their combined effects demonstrated a nearly twofold increase in total NO-synthase activity in the periodontal tissues of animals with combined exposure compared to the control group, and a 1.6-fold increase compared to rats with isolated obesity (Table 1).

The iNOS activity in the soft periodontal tissues of rats exposed to chronic stress on the background of obesity increased 2.42 times compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$) and 1.73 times compared to rats with isolated obesity. Furthermore, a 2.3-fold increase in iNOS activity compared to the control group was observed in rats subjected to chronic stress. The activity of the constitutive cNOS isoforms in the periodontal tissues of rats with obesity and the combined effects of obesity and stress did not significantly differ from that of the control group (Table 1).

Under these conditions, the content of stable nitrogen oxygen metabolites—nitrite anions—in the periodontal tissues of animals significantly increased in all study groups (Table 1).

Analyzing the degree of nitrosative stress in the periodontal tissues based on the peroxynitrite content, we observed a nearly threefold increase in peroxynitrite concentration in rats with combined exposure to obesity and stress compared to the control group, and a 1.6-fold increase compared to

animals with glutamate-induced obesity (Table 1).

Table 1

Indicators of nitrosative stress in the periodontal tissues of the study groups of rats
($\bar{x} \pm SE$, n = 77, study duration: 150 days).

Groups	NO synthase activity $\mu\text{mol/g} \cdot \text{min}$			NO ₂ content nmol/g	Content of nitrosothiols $\mu\text{mol/g}$	Peroxy-nitrite content (ONOO ⁻) $\mu\text{mol/g}$
	Total NOS activity	Constitutive NOS activity	Activity inducible NOS			
Control	0.287±0.038 ^a	0.081± 0.0005 ^b	0.208± 0.037 ^a	2.20±0.26 ^a	0.075± 0.0010	0.63±0.015 ^a
Obesity	0.372±0.113 ^b	0.080± 0.0008 ^a	0.291± 0.114	2.78±0.54 ^a	0.105± 0.0007 ^b	1.13±0.017 ^b
Obesity + stress	0.587±0.094 ^b	0.079± 0.0002 ^a	0.505± 0.091	2.63±0.17 ^a	0.087± 0.0015	1.83±0.022 ^b
Stress	0.573±0.066 ^b	0.098± 0.0009 ^b	0.475± 0.067 ^b	2.79±0.21 ^a	0.050± 0.0007 ^a	1.77±0.007 ^a
Nanocerium	0.298±0.073 ^b	0.056± 0.0002 ^a	0.241± 0.071	2.23±0.49 ^a	0.115± 0.0008 ^b	0.85±1.033 ^b
Obesity + nanocerium	0.289±0.052 ^a	0.066± 0.0005 ^a	0.223± 0.048	2.20±0.26 ^a	0.089± 0.0012 ^b	1.06±0.010 ^b
Obesity + stress+ nanocerium	0.344±0.051 ^b	0.079± 0.0002 ^a	0.265± 0.050 ^b	2.48±0.28 ^a	0.088± 0.0009	0.52±0.064 ^b
Stress + nanocerium	0.361±0.197	0.083± 0.0001	0.377± 0.196 ^b	2.39±0.64 ^b	0.056± 0.0010 ^a	1.04±0.020

Note: Values marked with different letters are significantly different from each other within a column of the table according to the Tukey's test with Bonferroni correction.

Reversible S-nitrosylation of cysteine or glutathione leads to the formation of S-nitrosothiols, which are signaling molecules that act as a depot of nitric oxide, facilitating its transfer over long distances. We established that the content of nitrosothiols in the periodontal tissues of animals with combined obesity and chronic stress increased by 1.2 times compared to the control group and rats with isolated obesity (Table 1).

The introduction of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide to one-month-old rats according to a scheme with two-week breaks over 3 months resulted in a significant 1.7-fold reduction in the overall NO-synthase activity in the periodontal tissues of animals with combined exposure compared to rats with chronic stress on the background of obesity without correction. The iNOS activity in the soft periodontal tissues of rats subjected to chronic stress on the background of obesity and cerium nanoparticle administration significantly decreased by almost 2 times.

Compared to this indicator in rats subjected to chronic stress on the background of obesity without cerium nanoparticle administration, the nanocrystalline cerium dioxide prevented the development of nitrosative stress in the periodontal tissues of animals under obesity and chronic stress conditions. This is evidenced by a significant 3.5-fold reduction in peroxy-nitrite content compared to the group of rats subjected to combined obesity and stress without cerium nanoparticle administration (Table 1).

Analyzing the activity of ornithine decarboxylase in the periodontal tissues of animals in the studied groups, we established a significant 1.6-fold increase in rats with combined obesity and chronic stress compared to the control group. The introduction of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide

under these conditions contributed to a 2.4-fold increase in ornithine decarboxylase activity compared to rats with obesity and stress without correction (Table 2).

Table 2

Activity of ornithine decarboxylase and arginase in the periodontal tissues of the studied rat groups ($\bar{x} \pm SE$, n = 77, duration of study – 150 days)

Groups	Ornithine decarboxylase activity, nmol/g*min	Arginase activity, $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}^*\text{h}$
Control	6.20±1.98 ^a	7.33±1.87
Obesity	9.63±2.44 ^b	8.97±1.52
Obesity + stress	9.99±2.08 ^{ab}	25.52±10.05 ^{ab}
Stress	35.07±18.11	6.12±0.99
Nanocerium	20.91±4.88	3.63±0.80 ^a
Obesity + nanocerium	12.18±4.46	5.96±1.19
Obesity + stress+ nanocerium	24.28±18.77 ^b	8.12±8.01 ^b
Stress + nanocerium	19.72±4.06	5.72±0.97

Note: Values marked with different letters are significantly different from each other within a column of the table according to the Tukey’s test with Bonferroni correction.

The maximum increase of 3.5 times in arginase activity in the periodontal tissues of animals was observed in rats with combined obesity and chronic stress compared to the control group and 2.8 times compared to the group of rats with glutamate-induced obesity. The introduction of nanocerium in these conditions significantly reduced arginase activity in the periodontal tissues of animals by 3 times compared to rats subjected to chronic stress on the background of obesity without nanocerium administration (Table 2).

An objective criterion for the development of pathological changes in the periodontal tissues of animals is the determination of the root exposure coefficient of molars as an indicator of the resorption of the alveolar process of the jaws. We found that under conditions of obesity, chronic stress, and their combined effects, the root exposure coefficient of molars significantly increased by 25%, 40%, 35% compared to the control group. The introduction of nanocerium prevented alveolar process resorption in all studied animal groups, as evidenced by a decrease in the root exposure coefficient of molars compared to rats in the corresponding groups without the introduction of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Root exposure coefficient of molars (%)

Group 1 – control, Group 2 – obesity, Group 3 – obesity + stress, Group 4 – stress, Group 5 – nanocerium, Group 6 – obesity + nanocerium, Group 7 – obesity + stress + nanocerium, Group 8 – stress + nanocerium

We found that the combined effect of glutamate-induced obesity and chronic stress leads to a significant increase in body weight, body mass index, Lee index, and visceral fat content in animals compared to the control group and isolated effects. Nanocrystalline cerium dioxide contributes to a significant reduction in visceral fat content in animals under conditions of obesity and chronic stress (Fig. 3, 4).

Fig. 3. Serial No. 56 (obesity+stress)

Fig. 4. Serial No. 2 (obesity+stress + nanocerium)

In the field of biomedical research, cerium-containing nanomaterials have attracted considerable attention due to their exceptional properties, particularly the high number of oxygen vacancies and their ability to undergo transformations between Ce (III) and Ce (IV) ions. These unique characteristics make cerium-based nanomaterials promising candidates for addressing problems associated with oxidative stress. The chemistry of rare-earth metals differs from that of other metals in the main group due to the nature and occupation of 4f orbitals, which in turn provides them with unique catalytic, magnetic, and electronic properties. Cerium oxide nanoparticles represent a new generation of artificial enzymes that have gained significant attention due to their nanocatalytic activity, low toxicity, and ability to easily adjust their electronic configurations in response to changes in the biological environment. These properties are derived from the rapid and targeted interconversion between Ce 4+ and Ce 3+, as well as oxygen vacancies in the lattice structure that arise from oxygen and/or electron loss during redox reactions. Due to this dual and regenerative role as an oxidation and reduction catalyst, numerous studies have demonstrated that nanocerium possesses various activities similar to antioxidant enzymes, including activities resembling superoxide dismutase, catalase, and peroxidase [18, 19]. Theoretical calculations have shown that oxygen vacancies on the surface of cerium dioxide reduce activation energy and the formation of transient particles, playing a crucial role in catalytic processes [20].

Singh N. et al. first proved that the nanoferrite cerium vanadate (CeVO₄) could replace the function of superoxide dismutase 1 and 2 in neuronal cells, even when the natural enzyme is inhibited. The nanoferrite cerium vanadate prevents mitochondrial damage in cells with a deficiency of superoxide dismutase 1 and 2 by regulating superoxide levels and restoring physiological levels of anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 family proteins. Additionally, the nanoferrite effectively prevents mitochondrial depolarization, leading to a significant increase in ATP levels in neurons during oxidative stress [21]. Cerium-based nanoferrites can effectively replace Cu, Zn-superoxide dismutase and Mn-superoxide dismutase in neuronal cells. The cerium-based nanoferrite CeVO₄ also prevents the oxidation of the key component of the inner mitochondrial membrane, cardiolipin, which plays an important role in mitochondrial processes [22].

Neonatal administration of glutamate to rats and modeling of immobilization-induced chronic stress contributed to an increase in body weight, body mass index, and Lee index compared to these

indicators in control animals and in rats with isolated effects of obesity and stress. Administration of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide prevented fat accumulation in the visceral compartment of rats. Nanocrystalline cerium dioxide prevented the increase in overall NO synthase activity in the periodontal tissues of animals with chronic stress in the context of obesity by reducing the activity of iNOS and prevented the development of nitrosative stress in the periodontal tissues, as evidenced by a significant reduction (3.5 times) in peroxynitrite levels compared to the group of rats subjected to combined obesity and stress without nanocerium administration.

In mammals, nitric oxide (NO) is an important signaling molecule with pleiotropic effects, playing various roles in both physiological and pathological processes [23]. One of the most important functions of NO is vasodilation, neurotransmission, regulation of gene transcription, post-translational protein modification, and more. An important process is the inactivation of NO through its reaction with superoxide radicals, resulting in the formation of peroxynitrite. Peroxynitrite is known to form as a result of the reaction between superoxide anion radicals and nitric oxide, and is a potent oxidant capable of attacking all biomolecules. Peroxynitrite modifies proteins by oxidizing or nitrating tyrosine, tryptophan, methionine, and other amino acid residues [24].

We found that the maximum increase in arginase activity (3.5 times) in the soft tissues of the periodontal tissues of animals occurred in rats subjected to the combined effect of obesity and chronic stress compared to the control and 2.8 times compared to the group of animals with glutamate-induced obesity. Arginase, a metalloenzyme, hydrolyzes L-arginine to urea and L-ornithine. Various pro-inflammatory factors, as well as interleukins, stimulate increased expression of arginase. Increased arginase activity, in turn, leads to the consumption of L-arginine, which is essential for the synthesis of nitric oxide by endothelial NO synthase. Extensive evidence has convincingly shown that increased arginase activity is associated with endothelial dysfunction in large blood vessels. Arginase inhibition increases NO bioavailability and reduces superoxide levels, improving endothelial function [25].

Arginase inhibits nitric oxide production through several potential mechanisms, including competition with NO synthase for the substrate L-arginine, inhibition of translation and stability of induced NO synthase, generation of urea, and sensitization of NO synthase to its endogenous inhibitor, asymmetric dimethyl-L-arginine [26].

Considering the biochemical properties of arginase and NO synthase, it supports the idea that arginase can inhibit NO synthesis by competing with NO synthase for L-arginine. Despite the fact that the affinity of L-arginine for NO synthase is much higher ($K_m \sim 2\text{--}20 \mu\text{M}$) than for arginase ($K_m \sim 1\text{--}5 \text{mM}$), the maximum arginase activity exceeds NO synthase activity by more than 1000 times, which indicates similar substrate usage rates at physiological L-arginine concentrations [27]. In fact, early studies on arginine metabolism by activated macrophages showed that most L-arginine is used for urea synthesis rather than NO, and that inhibiting arginase or adding L-arginine to the environment leads to increased NO synthesis. Recently, it was shown that arginase inhibition stimulates NO synthesis in endothelial cells. Furthermore, excessive expression of arginase I or arginase II inhibits NO generation in endothelial cells, which is associated with a significant reduction in intracellular L-arginine content [28]. Interestingly, constitutive expression of arginase in microvascular endothelial cells counteracts NO-mediated vasodilation, indicating that arginase serves a tonic vasoconstrictor function [29].

Administering nanocrystalline cerium dioxide to rats under glutamate-induced obesity and chronic stress conditions led to a significant reduction (threefold) in arginase activity in the periodontal tissues compared to rats under the same conditions without nanocerium administration.

We found that obesity and chronic stress, both individually and in combination, contribute to the resorption of the alveolar ridge in animal mandibles. Nanocrystalline cerium dioxide exhibits an anti-resorptive effect, as evidenced by a significant decrease in the molar root exposure coefficient in all studied groups of rats. Wei F. et al. demonstrated that rats treated with nanocerium were able to maintain bone tissue architecture, volume, and strength *in vivo* despite ionizing radiation exposure. Overall, nanocerium, according to the authors, may represent a new multifunctional therapeutic strategy for preventing bone tissue damage caused by ionizing radiation [30].

Therefore, in general consensus, nanocerium suppresses inflammatory signals while enhancing anti-inflammatory signaling pathways, promoting anti-inflammatory effects. Nanocerium is a multifunctional nanoferrite that exhibits additional bioactivity such as phosphatase activity,

which likely mediates some of its anti-inflammatory effects. Since the anti-inflammatory activity of nanocerium is potentially a pharmacological breakthrough, it is important to precisely attribute the described effects to specific functions of their nanoferrites, thereby achieving therapeutic validity. Chronic inflammation is the cause of most diseases and is currently recognized as the leading cause of death worldwide [31]. In 2009, Hirst S. et al. were among the first to propose nanocerium as a potentially effective therapeutic agent against inflammation, showing that it inhibits lipopolysaccharide-induced oxidative stress and inflammation in animal macrophages [32]. Since then, the number of in vitro and in vivo reports demonstrating that nanocerium can significantly alleviate a wide range of inflammatory pathologies has increased. These effects are generally attributed to the antioxidant properties of nanocerium, which is a plausible explanation since oxidative stress plays a primary role in inflammation, and the unique SOD- and catalase-mimetic activity of nanocerium is sufficient to ensure its anti-inflammatory properties. However, nanocerium is a multifunctional nanoenzyme that performs additional redox and non-redox functions, including phosphatase, haloperoxidase, photolyase, and oxidase-like activities, which occur independently of catalase/SOD-mimetic activity [33].

Thus, our study demonstrated the experimental effectiveness of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide in preventing the development of nitrosative stress in the periodontal tissues of animals subjected to chronic stress in the context of obesity and preventing alveolar ridge resorption in the mandibles of rats. Our findings are supported by [34], who demonstrated the antioxidant potential of cerium nanoparticles in the treatment of periodontitis, confirming their safety. These effects include protection against cell damage induced by oxidative stress through modulation of pro-inflammatory mediators and inhibition of the NF- κ B pathway, as well as induction of macrophage transition from the M1 to M2 phenotype [35]. Studies have shown that nanocerium possesses anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties by inhibiting the MAPK-NF- κ B signaling pathway and renewing Nrf2 signaling in a model of lipopolysaccharide-induced periodontitis in rats [36].

In conclusion, periodic administration of nanocrystalline cerium dioxide to rats after neonatal glutamate and chronic stress exposure significantly improved biochemical parameters, prevented the development of nitrosative stress in periodontal tissues, and contributed to the anti-resorptive effect.

Conclusions

The combined effect of obesity and chronic stress significantly increased the overall NO synthase activity in the periodontal tissues of rats compared to isolated effects.

The increase in NO synthase activity in the periodontal tissues of animals under combined obesity and chronic stress was due to a significant rise in inducible NO synthase activity. The maximum concentration of peroxynitrites in the periodontal tissues was observed in animals with chronic stress under obesity conditions.

Nanocerium significantly reduced the activity of inducible NO synthase and the content of peroxynitrites in the periodontal tissues of animals subjected to the combined effect of obesity and chronic stress compared to rats with induced obesity and chronic stress without correction. Nanocerium demonstrated an anti-resorptive effect on the periodontal bone tissue in rats under obesity, chronic stress, and their combined effects.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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